

**ПОЛИСАХАРИДЛАР АСОСИДА ОЛИНГАН МАҲСУЛОТЛАРНИНГ
ТИББИЁТДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ****Миркозижон Нишонов**

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада республикамизда полисахаридлар асосида биологик фаол маҳсулотлар олиши соҳасида эришилган ютуқлар ва уларнинг тиббиётда қўлланилиши ҳақида батафсил маълумотлар келтирилган

Калим сўзлар: Полисахарид, целлюлоза, биологик фаоллик, бактерицид хосса, тиббиёт

Abstract. This article provides detailed information about the achievements in the field of obtaining biologically active products based on polysaccharides in our republic and their use in medicine.

Keywords: Polysaccharide, cellulose, biological activity, bactericidal property, medicine

The didactic processing of information about the importance and use of the products obtained in the chemical industry and their use in the national economy, including in medicine, are detailed in the literature [1-10].

In this article, we will dwell in detail on the substance that is a component of cotton and similar fibrous plants - polysaccharide-cellulose, and on its basis, obtaining biologically active substances and their use in medicine.

There is a lot of literature on cellulose and its derivatives. Because in our country, the discoveries made by the scientists of the Cotton Cellulose Chemistry and Technology Scientific Research Institute have made it possible to create several volumes of literature in this field. However, the work in Uzbekistan related to the discovery of biologically active cellulose products was not sufficiently publicized.

Obtaining cellulose products used in medicine has been of interest to most of our scientists for a long time. The work carried out in this area is yielding effective results.

Below we will talk about new cellulose products with excellent properties.

Academician H. U. Usmanov, a scientific and technical figure who served in the republic for effective scientific and research work aimed at improving the properties of cellulose in our country, professor of the National University of Uzbekistan A. A. Yolchiboev, professor of the Tashkent Textile and Light Industry Institute, led by the B. E. Gellers. It is continued today by their students.

Scientists are working with cotton and wood cellulose in different chemical ways and getting amazing products from them. These methods are called chemical modification methods. Chemists refer to modified cellulose products as cellulose copolymers. Cellulose products made by methods such as esterification, alkylation, and obtaining cellulose graft copolymers with a network-like structure do not rot, absorb water well, do not burn, are not affected by sunlight and other rays, are not affected by microorganisms, embody thermoplastic properties, and have cation-anion exchange properties. will have, will paint well. Below we will talk about cellulose products used in the medical field.

Cellulose-based bactericidal products are products that are not affected by bacteria.

Ordinary cotton cellulose quickly rots under the influence of various microbes, completely losing its original properties. Chemists call this process biochemical destruction. If ordinary cotton cellulose is treated with various chemical substances, depending on the nature of the substances, cellulose and fabrics made from it will not be affected by bacteria and various microbes, and will have the property of destroying them. Because as a result of the inclusion of various functional groups in the composition of the cellulose macromolecule or their chemical bonding, they have the property of biological activity. Since most of them have the property of dissolving well in water, the biologically active substances formed as a result of the hydrolysis process kill various microbes or prevent their reproduction.

Scientists thoroughly studied the processes of the formation of cellulose products and the reasons why they have bactericidal properties when used in medicine, and came to the following conclusion: if the organic substance introduced into the cellulose macromolecule is ionically bonded to the cellulose macromolecule, the cellulose copolymer is easily hydrolyzed in water and has biologically active properties. . If the substance introduced with cellulose has formed a covalent bond, its solubility in water decreases, therefore, it cannot be hydrolyzed. Therefore, it is believed that such cellulose preparations do not have biological activity.

It is possible to use natural and artificial polymers to create fibers and materials with bactericidal properties. The work in this field was first used by Meos and Wolflar, scientists of the St. Petersburg Institute of Light Industry. They were able to impart bactericidal properties to the fibers made on the basis of polyvinyl alcohol. On the basis of these discoveries, synthetic fibers were synthesized in factories with bactericidal properties.

As a result of the joint work of chemists and medical scientists, fibers and fabrics made on the basis of polyethylene terephthalate, fluorolon and polyvinyl alcohol, which are easily soluble in water, are widely used in medicine. For example, the previously cut body was sewn in special silks, and after a certain time, the patient went to the doctor to remove it. Fibers made of polymers are absorbed by the body after a certain time. Since these types of fibers are quite expensive, scientists have raised the issue of whether it is possible to use cotton cellulose for these purposes Academician of the Republican Academy of Sciences H.U.Usmonov.

Our scientists, in cooperation with doctors, have developed a leucoplaster that binds bandages and wounds with bactericidal properties. These products are of great importance in the rapid recovery of patients. Because these products, firstly, serve to bind the wounded organisms, and secondly, they ensure rapid healing of wounds due to the fact that they kill various bacteria there.

The use of bactericidal cellulose products in medicine and the achievements in its use do not end there. Scientists are looking for ways to get rid of various diseases from these products.

REFERENCES

1. 1.M. M. Yunusov, M.Nishonov. Studying the Efficiency of Teaching the Chemical Technology Course Using Information Technologies. Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching, (2022). 13,33–38.
2. M.Nishonov, Sh.Mamajonov, V.Xujaev – Kimyo o'qitish metodikasi. Toshkent: O 'qituvchi, 2002.

3. М.Ф. Нишанов, АА Хайдаров, Д.М. Мирзаев - [Значение изучения среды раствора при профессиональной подготовке студентов направления «Пищевая технология»](#). Журнал Universum: технические науки, 2020 Номер 10-2 (79) Страницы 92-94
4. M. Nishonov, S Mamajonov, D Tojimatov - [Methodological significance of studying the migration of microelements in water and soils](#). American Journal of Applied Science and Technology, 2022 Том2 Номер07 Страницы10-14
5. М.Нишонов,С.Тешабоев.[Мактабда кимёдан амалий ишлар](#). - Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1992,134 бет
6. Nishonov, M., & Yunusov, M. (2023).Ўзбекистон республикасида кимё саноатининг ривожланиши. Science and innovation, 2 (7), 315-322.
7. Yunusov, M. M. (2023). Teaching the course of sulphic acid production in industry with the help of pedagogical technologies. Conferencea, 90-93.
8. Yunusov, M. M. (2023). Increasing the efficiency of teaching the science of chemical technology on the base of pedagogical technologies. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 4(6), 465–468.
9. Nishonov, M., & Yunusov, M. M. Preparing future chemistry teachers to introduce reproduction. Дата публикации 2021/9/8. European journal of humanities and educational advancements (ejhea) available online at: <https://www.scholarzest.com>, 2(9), 94-97.
10. Nishonov, M., & Yunusov, M. M. (2021). Preparing future chemistry teachers to introduce reproduction. Дата публикации, 9, 8.